

PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION AND WAYS OF SCHOOL COOPERATION

Saidova Feruza Akramovna

Teacher of the Department of "Preschool, Primary and Special Training Methodologies" of the National Center for Teaching Educators to New Methodologies of Surkhandarya Region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7876635>

Abstract. *From the very first steps on the path to independence, our country has undergone radical political and economic reforms that cover all spheres of society. And if we take the field of education, great changes are also observed in the field of preschool education, which is considered its first step. The coherence between preschool and the school is reflected in the forms and methods of education. Today, this consistency is a matter of dosage. This article discusses preschool and school partnerships.*

Keywords: *upbringing, education, activity, children, age, play, law, ability.*

Preschool education is the initial stage of the continuous education system and is organized based on the requirements of the Law "On Education" and "On Preschool Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Pre-school education creates necessary organizational, methodological, psychological and pedagogical conditions for raising healthy, mature children in all aspects. Preparing children for regular education in school helps parents.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the improvement of the pre-school education system, the updating of the form, means and methods of the content of education.

Children's knowledge, skills and qualifications are checked at the end of each academic year through control exercises in the preschool educational organization. The school readiness level of children aged 6-7 is checked based on the indicators of the state requirements.

Preparing the children of the preparatory group to study at school occupies an important place. He completes his childhood in the pre-school period and begins the stage of learning, striving to study at school. At the same time, children's behavior and activities, which are important for further education related to their mental, spiritual-volitional, and emotional spheres, are actively formed. The main attention of the educator of the preparatory group is focused on the full mastery of the content of the preschool education program for all children, because this is a mandatory condition for full preparation for school education. Pedagogical process in large groups arising from the task of preparing children for school is unique.

This uniqueness is not only copying the educational work of the school, but also the special organization of children's activities and behaviors aimed at forming the qualities necessary for successful teaching at school.

When he comes to the preparatory group, the child begins to show himself independently in various activities: self-service, being on duty, working in the heart of nature. The child's independence and organizational skills are formed under the direct guidance of the educator in all their activities.

The main attention of the educator of the preparatory group is focused on the full mastery of the content of the preschool education program for all children, because this is a mandatory condition for full preparation for school education. Pedagogical process in large groups, arising

from the task of preparing children for school, is unique. This uniqueness is not only copying the educational work of the school, but also the special organization of children's activities and behaviors aimed at forming the qualities necessary for successful teaching at school.

When he comes to the preparatory group, the child begins to show himself independently in various activities: in self-service, on duty, in his work in the bosom of nature. The child's independence and organizational skills are formed under the direct guidance of the educator in all their activities.

The educator takes care of ensuring that children sleep and eat normally. An important condition for consistency in teaching methods is to achieve children's conscious acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, to develop their mental abilities and creative activity in kindergarten and school. A lot of methods used in the preschool education organization and in the primary class of the school are the same, and they are aimed at improving the mental, moral and willful development of children, at the same time, at the same time, they are interested in acquiring knowledge of new content, practical activities, and knowledge. increases and helps to acquire more complex forms of relationships with the teacher that arise during the lesson.

Such guidance of the teacher to the practical activities of the children during the activities, to the learning process is the basis of the consistency of the educational method between the school and the preschool educational organization.

Lessons at school, activities in preschool education organizations have some specific features, but at the same time, there is a commonality in the conduct of education on an organizational basis. The content of the activities and lessons is carried out on the basis of a specific program, clearly defined time allocation, the leadership role of the pedagogue, the use of scientifically based methods and methods of education, the ability to voluntarily control one's own behavior, the ability to engage in mental work aimed at a certain goal will go All these prepare the child to actively enter school education.

Thus, consistency in educational work between pre-school educational organizations and schools makes it possible to develop a child's personality in all ways with a clear goal.

Communication between the preschool educational organization and the school is carried out on the basis of two directions:

1. Communication between the pre-school education organization and the team of pedagogues of the school.
2. Bringing children of preschool education organization and primary school students closer to each other.

Elementary school students get acquainted with the content of the work carried out by senior and preparatory groups, and at the same time, they are based on the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by children in school education.

The main purpose of the establishment of interaction between preschool education organizations and school pedagogues is to prepare children for school education in accordance with the requirements of the times, and to establish preschool education with schools in educational and educational activities. It is to establish a strong relationship between the organization, to achieve high results in this field by deeply analyzing the educational and educational work carried out in the preschool organization and the school so that children can study successfully at school.

The content and forms of communication between the pre-school education organization and the school are determined depending on the above tasks.

The preschool organization and the school communicate with each other on pedagogical campaign, methodical and practical issues. Pedagogical campaign work to introduce the work of the educator of the school preparation group of the preschool education organization and the first grade teacher with the educational and educational work carried out in the school preparation group and the first grade of the preschool education organization, the content of the school preparation group and the 1st grade program, requires studying the characteristics of children of the preparatory group and students of the 1st grade at school. When working in this way, teachers and educators help the school to better understand the issues of preparing them for school by understanding the age characteristics of children in the preparatory group of the 1st grade and preschool educational organization, their mental nature, mental and social development.

In the implementation of this goal, concrete forms of communication are established between the preschool education organization and the school as follows: teachers and educators discuss the appropriateness of joint activities on preparing children for school and on issues of integrity. seminars, participation in pedagogical councils, as well as exchange of experience through lectures prepared by educators and teachers on the age characteristics of children, mental difficulties in their transition from preschool education organization to school, factors that help them adapt to school conditions without difficulty, and include others.

The pedagogic function of the organic connection between the preschool educational organization and the school requires mutual acquaintance with the forms and methods of educational activities carried out in the preparatory group of the preschool educational organization and in the 1st grade of the school.

The practical task of communication between the preschool educational organization and the school is that, on the one hand, the teacher goes to the preparatory group of the preschool educational organization and gets to know his future teachers, on the other hand, the educators of the preparatory group They learn how their former students are studying in the first grade. When following children to school, each child is given a clear description.

In this description, the educator reveals the unique characteristics of the development of each child, which helps the teacher to take the correct approach from the pedagogical point of view when dealing with the child. The educator, in turn, consistently communicates with the children who have gone to the 1st grade, directly participates in the lessons and determines how they are studying, their behavior, and the reason for their failure in studies by asking the teacher.

All of these allow the educator to find out the achievements and shortcomings of the educational work carried out with the children.

Educators and teachers exchange ideas by participating in city and district conferences for the purpose of disseminating best practices, campaigning and promotion.

The following conditions should be observed in order for the organic connection between the preschool education organization and the school to be effective. It is necessary that the communication between the pre-school education organization and the school should be carried out consistently, it should be long-term, the work to be carried out, the issues to be resolved should be planned.

The basis of cooperation is formed by a perspective plan for joint work, in which the main task, content, forms of work, time, and persons responsible for the implementation of the interaction should be specified.

As a result of establishing such a relationship between the school and the pre-school education organization throughout the year, it becomes especially important in the child's education.

There are various forms of bringing children closer to school students: organizing a school excursion, going to the school museum, classroom, library, workshop, joint activities, holiday mornings, music-art evenings, paintings and clay plasticine. organization of the exhibition of clothes and others are examples of these.

The educative and developing nature of education is a principle characteristic of modern education. It develops interest in knowledge and cognitive processes in children.

For this purpose, the knowledge, skills, and abilities given to children are improved with a certain consistency. As a result, children learn to perform actions according to the instructions and examples of adults, to apply the knowledge they have acquired before in new activities, to control and correctly evaluate their own behavior, work, behavior.

Children develop a conscious attitude to the task. Listening carefully to the teacher's explanations and instructions, striving for a good result in one's work, working carefully at a certain speed and consistency is formed, work ability increases.

During the activity, the educator takes into account the specific characteristics of each child's attention, thinking, memory, knowledge and skill level.

A special approach to the educational process requires gradual implementation of mental tasks and methods of their performance. For example, if a child cannot tell something by himself, the educator gives him a plan on the topic, and then instructs him to do the work independently. Shy, slow children are activated by a separate approach, and the task is complicated for children who master the material well.

So, the methods used in the school preparation group have their own characteristics. Demonstration methods are used here not only as a method of movement, but also to activate children's thinking.

For example, in the activity of landscape painting, showing an example is used at the beginning of the activity to revive the memory and image of the imagination, and at the end of the activity, it is used to check whether the work done and the painting is done correctly, in order to see the comparison with the example.

The oral method is of great importance in the proper combination of practical and game methods with the demonstration method in order for children to acquire knowledge thoroughly, to activate the educational process. Game methods, especially the method of didactic games, do not lose their importance. Because education is carried out through games, especially didactic games, children understand the educational task better, which increases their voluntary attention, activates activity and increases interest in learning.

In conclusion, it should be noted that working in children's development centers is the basis for preparing them for school education so that they grow up mature, mentally and physically, and become loyal to national values and traditions. creates, increases their interest in the profession. The uniqueness of the Uzbek family, oriental manners, customs, customs, national

values and traditions, education, and striving for spiritual maturity are incomparable. The place that creates the main ground for children's education and learning is their family.

REFERENCES

1. Makhmudova O.A., Makhmudova S.A. "Technologies of working with plastic materials in preschool education system". Study guide. "NISO POLYGRAPH". Tashkent, 2019- 120p.
2. Makhmudova O.A. "Methodology of teaching preschool children to draw". Study guide. "NISO POLYGRAPH" Tashkent, 2019-152 p.
3. Kumon Publishing. Geometry & Measurement Grade 1 PDF Math Workbook, Kumon Publishing, 2008 USA, – 80 p
4. Djuraeva D.R. Modern trends in education of children of preschool age. Methodological manual - T.: 2015.